

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA, NUTRITION KNOWLEDGE, AND SCHOOL FOOD ENVIRONMENT ON THE DIETARY PRACTICES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the multifaceted influences on adolescents' dietary behaviors is crucial for promoting healthier lifestyles during adolescence. This study investigated the influence of social media use, nutrition knowledge, and the school food environment on the dietary practices of senior high school students in a private sectarian institution in Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines. Employing a descriptive-correlational design, data were collected from 399 Grade 12 students through validated instruments. The questionnaires used are the following: General Nutrition Knowledge Questionnaire (GNKQ) to assess nutrition knowledge Adopted and modified from Paubsanon (2020), developed and validated by Parmenter and Wardle (1990) the Social Media Influence on Food Choices Questionnaire adapted from Kaplan (2010), the School Food Environment Scale adapted from Laska (2010), and a Dietary Practices Survey adopted from Block et al (2006). Results revealed that students exhibited generally low nutrition knowledge, while social media influence and dietary practices were rated high, and the school food environment was positively evaluated in terms of taste, affordability, and availability of healthy options. Multiple regression analysis indicated that social media use and the school food environment significantly predicted students' dietary practices, whereas nutrition knowledge did not show a significant effect. These findings emphasize that digital and institutional environments exert a stronger influence on adolescents' eating behaviors than individual nutrition knowledge alone. Thus, it is recommended that future research develop and evaluate integrated interventions that utilize both school-based programs and social media strategies to promote sustainable, healthy dietary practices among adolescents.

Keywords: *dietary practices, nutrition knowledge, school food environment, senior high students, social media*

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a formative stage in which lifelong dietary habits are established, making it a critical period for nutrition education and behavioral interventions. For senior high school students, the interplay of personal knowledge, peer influences, media exposure, and environmental factors significantly shapes their food choices. With the proliferation of social media platforms, adolescents are now more exposed than ever to food-related content, which can either promote healthy behaviors or contribute to misinformation and poor dietary decisions (Jeong et al., 2022; Law et al., 2023).

In the Philippine context, adolescent nutrition continues to be a pressing public health concern. Recent national surveys report that many Filipino students fail to meet the recommended intake of fruits, vegetables, and dairy products, often opting instead for processed, high-sugar, and high-fat alternatives (Angeles-Agdeppa et al., 2022). This alarming trend is compounded by inadequate nutrition knowledge, limited food literacy in the school curriculum, and inconsistent availability of healthy food options in the school environment (Ronto et al., 2021; Saribay et al., 2019).

However, several critical research gaps remain. While students may possess basic knowledge of nutritional requirements, this does not consistently translate into healthy eating behaviors. Many prioritize convenience, taste, time constraints, and cost over nutritional value, leading to poor food choices and weight management challenges. There is a lack of recent, in-depth analysis on why knowledge alone is insufficient and what additional factors or interventions might bridge this gap (Amore et al., 2019).

Social media platforms play a significant role in shaping dietary preferences, with recent studies showing that 65–75% of college students report being influenced by social media in their food choices, with girls being more affected than boys. Despite this, the specific mechanisms by which social media impacts dietary behaviors—and how these might be harnessed for positive change—are not fully understood and require further exploration using up-to-date data (Rachana et al., 2024).

The physical and policy environment of schools, including the availability and promotion of healthy versus unhealthy foods in dining facilities, vending machines, and à la carte programs, has a demonstrable impact on students' dietary habits. Yet, there is limited contemporary research examining the effectiveness of environmental interventions and how school-level factors can be optimized to promote healthy eating (Micha et al., 2020).

Commonly cited barriers to healthy eating among college students include a lack of time, limited healthy options, high prices of nutritious foods, and insufficient social support. Recent studies call for more nuanced, context-specific research to understand

how these barriers interact and what targeted strategies might effectively address them (Greaney et al., 2009).

Given these gaps, the present study is both timely and necessary. It aims to provide a comprehensive, updated analysis of the factors influencing dietary practices among senior high school students by integrating the latest findings and focusing on the interplay between knowledge, social media, and the school environment (Amore, 2019). This research is particularly relevant in the context of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 2 (Zero Hunger), which emphasizes the need for improved nutrition and sustainable food systems. By addressing the unique challenges faced by college students, this study not only contributes to individual health and academic success but also supports broader global efforts to ensure access to safe, nutritious, and sufficient food for all.

In summary, the justification for this study lies in the persistent and evolving challenges of promoting healthy eating among senior high school students, the demonstrable effect of dietary habits on health outcomes, and the urgent need for evidence-based interventions that reflect the realities of today's social and institutional environments. By addressing the identified research gaps with recent data and a holistic approach, this study seeks to generate actionable insights for policy, practice, and future research.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the influence of social media on college students' knowledge of their dietary practices. Moreover, this study seeks out answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of the senior high students' nutritional knowledge?
2. What is the extent of students' assessment of school food environment in terms of:
 - 2.1 Taste;
 - 2.2 Price; and
 - 2.3 Availability of healthy food options
3. To what extent do senior high students utilize social media in their dietary selection?
4. What is the participant's level of assessment on the dietary practices?
5. Do the extent of senior high students' nutrition knowledge, their utilization of social media in food selection from social media, and the school food environment significantly influence their dietary practices?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive correlational research design, which is appropriate for examining the strength and direction of relationships between variables without implying causality (Creswell et al., 2014). This design suited the study's objective

of determining how social media use for food selection, nutritional knowledge, and the school food environment influences the dietary practices of senior high school students. The study used a standardized survey questionnaire particularly the General Nutrition Knowledge Questionnaire (GNKQ) (developed by Parmenter and Wardle, 1999) contains 59 items to determine the students' level of knowledge on nutrition, it is a widely used tool for assessing an individual's understanding of nutrition principles, dietary guidelines, and the relationship between diet and health. The Social Media Influence Questionnaire (Vaterlaus, 2015) contains 25 items that gather information about the extent of the influence of social media on food selection. Each of the categories comprises ten items. The questionnaire on dietary practices which consists of 15 items was adapted from Vaterlaus and this questionnaire elicits the students' assessment of their level of dietary practices. The Questionnaire on Students' Perception of the School Food Environment by Laska (2010) will likewise be utilized to ascertain the assessment of students of the school food environment categorized into taste, price, and availability of healthy food options. Each of the categories comprises ten items. Questionnaire for Extent of Utilization of Social Media for Food Selection (Kaplan, 2010) consists of 11 questions.

RESULTS

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Nutrition Knowledge

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
74 – 88	Very High	0	0.00
56– 73	High	3	0.75
38 – 55	Moderate	27	6.77
19– 37	Low	206	51.63
1 – 18	Very Low	163	40.85
	Total	399	100.0
	Overall Mean	19.87	
	Interpretation	Low	
	SD	12.82	

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of School Food Environment in terms of Taste

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	86	21.55
3.51-4.50	High	153	38.35
2.51-3.50	Moderate	134	33.58

1.51-2.50	Low	22	5.51
1.00-1.50	Very Low	4	1.00
Total		399	100.0
Overall Mean		3.76	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.85	

Specific Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD
1 The food available at school is appealing to my taste.	3.78	High	0.98
2 I find the variety of flavors on the school menu satisfying.	3.72	High	0.98
3 The taste of the healthy food options at school is enjoyable.	3.79	High	0.96
4 The overall taste of the food at school meets my expectations.	3.74	High	0.97
5 I am satisfied with the freshness of the food available at school.	3.74	High	1.00
6 The food at school looks appealing to me.	3.72	High	0.97
7 The food at school tastes homemade.	3.88	High	0.98
8 I am satisfied with the smell of the food available at school.	3.82	High	0.97
9 The food at school is of high quality.	3.68	High	1.00
10 I feel satisfied after eating the food at school.	3.76	High	0.99

Table 3

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of School Food Environment in terms of Price

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very highly affordable	72	18.05
3.51-4.50	Highly affordable	143	35.84
2.51-3.50	Moderately affordable	160	40.10
1.51-2.50	Less affordable	20	5.01
1.00-1.50	Not affordable	4	1.00
Total		399	100.0
Overall Mean		3.66	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.82	

Specific Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD
1 The price of the food available at school is reasonable.	3.43	High	1.06

2	I find the cost of healthy food options at school affordable.	3.58	High	1.04
3	The value for money of the food at school is satisfactory.	3.53	High	1.00
4	The price of the food at school is a significant factor in my food choices.	3.64	High	1.03
5	I believe that the school should offer more affordable, healthy food options.	4.02	High	0.98
6	The price of the food at school is a barrier to choosing healthy options.	3.67	High	0.98
7	I am satisfied with the cost of the food available at school.	3.56	High	1.04
8	The price of the food at school is competitive compared to the food outside the school.	3.59	High	1.07
9	I am willing to pay more for healthier food options at school.	3.61	High	1.02
10	The school should provide more discounts on healthy food options.	3.93	High	0.99

Table 4

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of School Food Environment in terms of Availability of Healthy Food Options

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	85	21.30
3.51-4.50	High	161	40.35
2.51-3.50	Moderate	131	32.83
1.51-2.50	Low	19	4.76
1.00-1.50	Very Low	3	0.75
	Total	399	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.80	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.82	

Specific Indicators	<i>M</i>	Interpretation	<i>SD</i>
1 Healthy food options are always available at school.	3.74	High	0.97
2 I find it easy to access a variety of healthy food choices at school.	3.67	High	1.01
3 The school should increase the availability of fresh fruits and vegetables.	3.94	High	0.97

4	I am satisfied with the current availability of low-calorie food options at school.	3.71	High	0.97
5	The school should provide more information about the healthy food options available.	3.91	High	0.93
6	I am aware of all the healthy food options available at school.	3.77	High	0.96
7	The school should offer a wider range of healthy food options.	3.92	High	0.95
8	I am satisfied with the healthy food options available at school.	3.68	High	0.98
9	The school should improve the presentation of healthy food options.	3.89	High	0.92
10	I feel that the school prioritizes the availability of healthy food options.	3.80	High	0.98

Table 5

Summary Table of School Food Environment

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Taste	3.76	High	0.85
Price	3.66	High	0.82
Availability of healthy food options	3.80	High	0.82
School food environment	3.74	High	0.78

Table 6

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Extent of Senior High Students' Utilization of Social Media in their Dietary Selection

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	85	21.30%
3.51-4.50	High	161	40.35%
2.51-3.50	Moderate	131	32.83%
1.51-2.50	Low	19	4.76%
1.00-1.50	Very Low	3	0.75%
	Total	399	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.71	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.67	

Specific Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD
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1	I spend a significant amount of time on social media every day.	4.02	High	0.95
2	I frequently encounter food-related content on social media.	3.97	High	0.97
3	I actively search for food recommendations on social media.	3.76	High	1.05
4	I have tried a food product, dish, or recipe because it was trending on social media.	3.79	High	1.07
5	Social media features strongly influence my food selection.	3.71	High	1.08
6	I often purchase or try food items promoted on social media.	3.68	High	1.10
7	I encourage friends or family to try food products or recipes I find on social media.	3.75	High	1.08
8	Social media plays a significant role in shaping my food choices.	3.79	High	1.05

Table 7

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment on the Dietary Practices

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	79	19.80
3.51-4.50	High	158	39.60
2.51-3.50	Moderate	144	36.09
1.51-2.50	Low	15	3.76
1.00-1.50	Very Low	3	0.75
	Total	399	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.71	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.80	

Specific Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD
1 I eat three balanced meals a day.	3.47	High	1.21
2 I consume breakfast regularly.	3.46	High	1.31
3 I consume homemade meals more than fast food.	3.80	High	1.07
4 I include fruits in my daily diet.	3.52	High	1.11
5 I consume at least one serving of vegetables daily.	3.62	High	1.11
6 I check nutrition labels before purchasing food products.	3.45	High	1.21

7	I drink at least 8 glasses of water per day.	3.67	High	1.10
8	I limit my intake of sugary drinks like soda and artificial fruit juices.	3.57	High	1.15
9	I prioritize water over other beverages when feeling thirsty.	3.92	High	1.03
10	I eat a variety of food groups in my meals.	3.78	High	1.08
11	I prefer home-cooked meals over fast food.	3.93	High	1.00
12	I eat food with less salt and sugar.	3.58	High	1.09
13	I drink milk or consume calcium-rich foods (e.g., yogurt, cheese).	3.79	High	1.05
14	I eat protein-rich foods such as fish, eggs, poultry, or beans daily.	3.96	High	0.99
15	I choose lean meats or plant-based protein options.	3.67	High	1.01
16	I eat snacks only when I feel hungry, not out of boredom.	3.74	High	1.13
17	I avoid eating sugary snacks between meals.	3.54	High	1.13
18	I choose healthy snacks like fruits, nuts, or yogurt instead of chips and sweets.	3.58	High	1.08
19	I limit my intake of fried and oily foods.	3.51	High	1.10
20	I eat desserts and sweets in moderation.	3.73	High	1.02
21	I try to follow a healthy diet most of the time.	3.60	High	1.08
22	I am aware of the importance of a balanced diet.	4.02	High	0.96
23	I consciously make an effort to eat nutritious foods.	3.76	High	1.03
24	I feel that my diet directly affects my energy and performance in school.	3.90	High	0.98
25	I am willing to improve my eating habits for better health.	4.08	High	0.99

Table 8

Regression Analysis on the Influence of Participants' Assessment of Nutrition Knowledge, their Utilization of Social Media in Food Selection, and School Food Environment on their Dietary Practices

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.808	.186		4.341	.000

Taste	.036	.073	.039	.497	.619
Price	.201	.079	.201	2.55*	.011
Availability of healthy food options	.262	.075	.268	3.49**	.001
Social media utilization	.259	.058	.216	4.47**	.000
Nutrition Knowledge	.004	.002	.057	1.475	.141

Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	p
.647 ^a	.419	.412	56.69**	.000

** Significant at 0.01 level

* Significant at 0.05 level

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the level of the senior high students' nutritional knowledge?

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, and descriptive statistics on the participants' level of nutritional knowledge. The overall mean score was 19.87 ($SD = 12.82$), which falls within the "Low" category. This indicates that, on average, senior high school students possess a limited understanding of basic nutrition concepts, reflecting a broader deficiency in nutrition literacy. Such a result implies that the current educational support may be insufficient in equipping students with the knowledge required for informed dietary choices.

A more detailed examination of the distribution reveals that 51.63% of students were classified under the "Low" category, while 40.85% were in the "Very Low" category. Combined, this accounts for over 92% of the student population, highlighting a gap in essential nutrition knowledge. Only 6.77% demonstrated a "Moderate" level of understanding, and fewer than 1% were classified as "High." Notably, none of the participants achieved a "Very High" score.

These findings denote that a majority of students are less prepared to make sound nutritional decisions. This is consistent with the findings of Saribay et al. (2019), who reported that approximately 65% of Filipino high school students had low nutrition knowledge. This was attributed to the insufficient integration of health and nutrition education in the curriculum and the lack of accessible resources for adolescents (WHO, 2020).

Further supporting this concern, Ali et al. (2023) emphasized that school-based nutrition education improves adolescents' knowledge and dietary behaviors. In their

study, students exposed to structured programs were more likely to engage in healthier food choices. Ronto et al. (2021) also found that adolescents with low nutrition knowledge tended to consume more ultra-processed and high-sugar foods due to a lack of awareness and the strong influence of marketing and social media.

The implications of poor nutrition knowledge extend beyond dietary habits. Chacón-Cuberos et al. (2020) found that students with inadequate nutritional understanding were less likely to maintain a healthy body weight and were at higher risk for lifestyle-related illnesses. A more recent study by Foulsham et al. (2023) in Southeast Asia similarly linked poor nutrition knowledge to increased intake of processed foods and reduced intake of fruits and vegetables, underscoring a concerning pattern.

The minimal percentage of students falling under the "Moderate" and "High" categories likely indicates limited or sporadic exposure to nutrition education, possibly gained through individual efforts, external programs, or family influence. The complete absence of students in the "Very High" category reinforces the existence of a systemic gap in the delivery and effectiveness of nutrition education within the school setting.

Reflecting on the data, it is deeply concerning that more than 90% of students fall into the "Low" or "Very Low" categories of nutrition knowledge. This not only underscores the reality that adolescents are unequipped to make informed dietary choices, but also highlights a systemic failure in integrating effective nutrition education into the school curriculum. As someone who values the importance of health literacy, it is alarming to see such a stark deficiency, especially at a stage in life where habits begin to solidify. The absence of any student in the "Very High" category indicates that exposure to nutrition knowledge is either minimal, inconsistent, or largely ineffective. These findings reinforce the need for urgent reform in how schools approach health and nutrition instruction, particularly through accessible, engaging, and age-appropriate programs.

Beyond just knowledge gaps, the implications of this deficiency are far-reaching. Poor nutrition understanding not only leads to unhealthy food choices but also increases the risk of obesity, diabetes, and other lifestyle-related illnesses in the long term. It is particularly troubling to consider that students may unknowingly consume high-sugar or highly processed foods simply due to lack of awareness or susceptibility to misleading marketing. These insights push me to advocate for more structured, practical, and inclusive nutrition education—one that empowers students not just to memorize facts but to apply knowledge in real-life contexts. The role of schools, teachers, parents, and even media must be aligned to cultivate an environment where nutritional literacy becomes a basic life skill for every adolescent.

In light of these findings, there is a clear need to enhance the delivery of nutrition education in the school system. This may include integrating nutrition content across subjects, providing teacher training, and incorporating media literacy to help students critically evaluate food information encountered online. Such efforts would not only address current knowledge gaps but also promote long-term health and well-being.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of students' assessment of the school food environment in terms of:

2.1 Taste;

2.2 Price; and

2.3 Availability of healthy food options

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' assessment of the school food environment in terms of taste. The overall mean score of 3.76, with a standard deviation of 0.85, indicates a high level of assessment of the taste of food offered in the school environment. This denotes that students generally find the food taste appealing, highlighting the importance of food quality in influencing dietary choices.

Most participants (38.35%) rated the taste as high, while 21.55% rated it as very high, reflecting a positive perception of the food quality. The remaining 33.58% rated it as moderate, indicating some variation in taste satisfaction. Ha et al. (2022) state that taste is one of the most critical factors in students' perception of their school food environment. While school meals have improved nutritional quality over the past decade, many students still judge meals primarily by flavor. This supports the study of Poole et al. (2021) systematic review identifies strategies to improve school meal consumption, emphasizing that modifying menus to enhance palatability can increase participation rates. These findings underscore the importance of balancing nutritional improvements with efforts to make meals more appealing to students' taste preferences.

Findings show that for children and adolescents, food taste is a primary determinant of choice, whereas healthfulness is often secondary. A smaller proportion of students, 5.51%, rated the taste as low, and only 1.00% rated it as very low, indicating that while most students are satisfied, there is still room for improvement. The relatively higher standard deviation (0.85) indicates a spread of responses, highlighting that while the general assessment is high, there is a range of opinions among the students.

The findings align with the notion that the taste of food plays a significant role in students' dietary practices. Mikkelsen et al. (2020) further emphasize the importance of food taste in influencing children's and adolescents' food choices and dietary behaviors. The study found that when food is both appealing in taste and nutritionally balanced, students are more likely to adopt healthier eating patterns.

Among the specific indicators, "*The food at school tastes homemade*" received the highest mean score ($M = 3.88$, $SD = 0.98$), highlighting students' strong appreciation for the authenticity and quality of the food served. Students widely report that fresher, higher-quality ingredients improve taste. This finding supports the findings in the survey that the youth emphasize "higher quality ingredients; improved freshness and taste" as top needs for a better school meal experience (FitzSimons et. Al, 2025). Meals prepared from scratch with fresh components tend to be more palatable, whereas pre-packaged or reheated foods can taste stale or bland. This finding aligns with research by Mikkelsen et al. (2020), which emphasized that food perceived as homemade or freshly prepared is

often rated higher by consumers, particularly among younger populations.

These behavioral patterns can be further explained using Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986), which highlights that behavior is influenced by a dynamic interaction between personal factors, environmental influences, and behavior itself. The taste and sensory experience of food function as environmental reinforcers, which either encourage or discourage certain eating behaviors. If students consistently associate school meals with poor taste, their willingness to participate in meal programs diminishes, regardless of the nutritional content.

In conclusion, the findings reinforce that flavorful, freshly prepared, and high-quality meals have a strong impact on students' dietary decisions. Integrating theoretical models like Social Cognitive Theory helps contextualize the findings and underscores the importance of taste as both a behavioral cue and a modifiable element of the school food environment that can lead to more nutritious outcomes.

The second-highest rating, regarding satisfaction with the smell of the food ($M=3.82$), reflects the importance of aroma in shaping food preferences. Gallo et al. (2020) emphasized that pleasant food smells serve as powerful sensory cues, enhancing appetite and shaping students' initial judgments about food quality. A well-received aroma can improve students' openness to trying new or healthier dishes, especially when combined with appealing presentation.

In contrast, two indicators received the lowest mean scores: "*The food at school is of high quality*" ($M = 3.68$, $SD = 1.00$) and "*The food available at school is appealing to my taste*" ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.98$). Although these ratings still fall within the "High" category, they are relatively lower compared to others, signaling areas for improvement in students' perceptions of meal quality and taste appeal.

The lower score on food quality denotes that while students may enjoy certain sensory elements (such as smell or variety), they might have concerns regarding ingredients, freshness, or preparation methods. This finding agrees with the study of Cohen et al. (2021), who found that students' perception of food quality influences both their satisfaction and trust in school meal programs. Quality concerns, even when taste is acceptable, can reduce participation and lead students to seek food from external or less healthy sources.

Similarly, the relatively lower score for taste appeal may reflect inconsistencies in flavor or seasoning across meals, especially when compared to homemade or commercially available food. This resonates with findings by Delley and Brunner (2020), who highlighted that even when healthy meals are offered, if they lack consistent and culturally appropriate taste profiles, student satisfaction and consumption rates decline.

The findings resonate with my personal belief that taste plays a powerful role in shaping students' eating habits, especially during adolescence when preferences are still developing. It is clear that even if healthy options are available, students are less likely to

choose them unless they find the food enjoyable. The strong appreciation for meals that taste homemade reflects a deeper need for freshness, authenticity, and quality in school meals—factors that can make or break participation in school feeding programs. This insight reminds me that nutrition interventions must not only be guided by health goals but also by students' sensory experiences. As Social Cognitive Theory suggests, the food environment—including the taste and appearance of meals—can reinforce or hinder healthy behaviors. Therefore, improving flavor through better ingredients and preparation methods should be a central part of school nutrition strategies, ensuring that health and satisfaction go hand in hand.

Overall, these findings suggest that while students generally appreciate the sensory experience of school meals, particularly their homemade-like qualities, aroma, and taste of healthy options, there remain opportunities to improve perceived food quality and overall flavor appeal. Enhancing meal planning to focus on consistent taste, freshness, and quality assurance may further strengthen students' positive perceptions of food taste.

Table 3 shows that students' assessment of the price of school food yielded a mean score of 3.66, which means that students find the pricing highly favorable. This implies that, on average, students find the cost of food at school to be reasonable and within reach. The distribution of responses shows that 40.10% rated price as Moderate, and a substantial portion, 35.84%, rated it High. Additionally, 18.05% of students felt prices were *Very High* in terms of fairness, meaning they were very satisfied with the affordability.

Only a small fraction perceived the prices negatively, with 5.01% rating Low and 1% Very Low. The fact that over half of the students responded with high and very high satisfaction indicates that the majority view the school food as good value for money. However, the large *Moderate* group suggests that a significant number have some reservations, perhaps finding certain items expensive or feeling their budget is somewhat strained.

Across all ten indicators, students' responses consistently fell within the "High" category. The highest-rated statement was "*I believe that the school should offer more affordable, healthy food options*" ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.98$), underscoring strong student demand for accessible, nutritious meals. This aligns with the findings of Bleich et al. (2020), who noted that adolescents, particularly from low- to middle-income families, are more likely to consume healthier food if it is affordable and supported by school policies. Their study emphasized that cost is essential for food selection among students, especially when competing with inexpensive but less nutritious alternatives.

The Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986) also provides a useful lens, emphasizing the interaction between personal factors, behavior, and environmental influences. Affordability is a key environmental factor that can either enable or hinder healthy eating behaviors. The high rating of the statement "The school should provide more discounts on healthy food options" ($M = 3.93$, $SD = 0.99$) illustrates students'

awareness of the environmental barriers to healthy behavior, and their belief that price promotions could positively shape their food choices—consistent with Driessen et al. (2021), who found that economic incentives such as subsidies significantly increased students' purchase of healthy items.

Furthermore, the Ecological Model of Health Behavior (McLeroy et al., 1988) supports the understanding that behavior is influenced by multiple levels, particularly the institutional level in this study—namely the school food environment. The finding that students rated “The price of the food at school is a barrier to choosing healthy options” with a mean of 3.67 ($SD = 0.98$) signals the importance of institutional efforts to reduce financial barriers. As Kenney et al. (2020) and Micha et al. (2020) argue, the school's role in subsidizing healthier options is critical in ensuring equitable access, especially in socioeconomically disadvantaged settings.

Further support is found in the work of Micha et al. (2020), who advocate for institutional food environments, such as schools, to actively counteract the higher cost of healthy food by providing subsidized options that promote equity in access.

Interestingly, the lowest-rated item was “*The price of the food available at school is reasonable*” ($M = 3.43$, $SD = 1.06$). Although still falling under the “High” category, it suggests some reservations regarding the perceived value or consistency of food pricing. This might reflect variation in portion sizes, perceived freshness, or comparison with off-campus food options. Cohen et al. (2021) noted that perceived value for money, including food quality and satisfaction, is a significant factor in shaping students' food choices and participation in school meal programs.

This finding gave me a deeper appreciation of how affordability is not just about absolute price but about perceived value, especially for students who rely on school meals as a primary food source. It is encouraging that most students view school food as reasonably priced, but the large number of “Moderate” responses suggests that economic concerns still influence food decisions, particularly when students are weighing cost against quality, portion size, or taste. The high demand for more affordable healthy options clearly reflects a desire for nutritious choices that don't strain their budget.

Personally, it highlights how pricing strategies—such as offering discounts or subsidies—can be powerful tools for promoting healthier behaviors. Using theories like the Social Cognitive Theory and the Ecological Model of Health Behavior, I now understand how the school, as an institution, plays a crucial role in shaping not just knowledge but access and habits. Schools must look beyond nutritional content and consider how students' financial realities interact with the food environment, which directly impacts their eating choices.

In summary, the findings underscores that while students generally find school food prices acceptable, there is a clear demand for making healthier food options more affordable. This aligns with existing literature highlighting affordability as a critical determinant of students' food choices. When nutritious meals are priced beyond students'

reach, they tend to choose lower-cost, less healthy alternatives, compromising dietary quality and institutional nutrition objectives.

Therefore, implementing strategies such as targeted subsidies, reduced pricing for healthy items, and ongoing price monitoring could significantly enhance students' access to nutritious meals. These efforts not only address economic barriers but also promote better health behaviors, increase meal participation, and support the overarching goal of fostering a healthier school food environment, as reinforced by studies like that of Johnson et al. (2019).

Table 4 presents the students' assessment of healthy food availability in school, yielding an overall mean of $M = 3.80$ ($SD = 0.82$), interpreted as High. This reflects a generally favorable view of the school's efforts in offering nutritious food options.

Notably, 61.65% of students rated the availability as High or Very High, while 32.83% gave a Moderate rating. Only a small fraction (5.51%) reported Low or Very Low availability, suggesting that although the food environment is largely supportive, a subset of students still perceives gaps, possibly due to inconsistent access or limited variety.

Across specific indicators, all ten items were rated High, reinforcing the overall perception. Students agreed that healthy options are always available ($M = 3.74$) and easily accessible ($M = 3.67$). Satisfaction with low-calorie food options ($M = 3.71$) and awareness of healthy offerings ($M = 3.77$) also scored consistently high. However, responses suggesting areas for improvement received the highest mean scores: the need to increase the availability of fresh fruits and vegetables ($M = 3.94$), broaden the range of healthy food options ($M = 3.92$), and provide more information about these offerings ($M = 3.91$). These results indicate that while students appreciate what is currently offered, they are also calling for greater variety and better communication.

Interestingly, students reported a relatively high level of awareness about healthy food options yet simultaneously expressed a desire for more information. This apparent contradiction may reflect differences in students' levels of health consciousness or engagement. While some may already be well-informed, others may lack sufficient knowledge, signaling a need for more effective communication strategies, such as enhanced menu labeling, visual prompts, or student-led awareness campaigns.

The perception that the school prioritizes healthy food availability ($M = 3.80$) denotes that students recognize institutional support. However, the slightly lower mean for overall satisfaction ($M = 3.68$) indicates there is still room for improvement. This gap could be addressed by increasing food variety, ensuring a consistent supply of healthy choices, and offering alternatives that cater to diverse dietary needs.

These findings are supported by literature that emphasizes the critical role schools play in shaping student eating behaviors. Poole et al. (2021) found that implementing nutrition standards that increase the availability of healthy foods in schools positively affects students' dietary behaviors. Similarly, Mikkelsen et al. (2020) found that

greater availability of fruits and vegetables in school settings is associated with improved dietary quality among adolescents. The present results reflect this relationship, with students expressing both satisfaction and a desire for further enhancement, especially in terms of variety and visibility.

The student feedback offers a clear direction for improvement. Poole et al., (2021) states that schools may benefit from expanding the range of healthy options by rotating different fruits, offering new recipes, and accommodating various dietary preferences. Promotion strategies could be enhanced through clear labeling, daily menu highlights, or nutrition-focused signage. Additionally, consistent access to these options is essential to building student trust and engagement with school meals.

These findings also support the stronger implementation of nutrition policies. The findings would recommend schools to regularly review and refine their food offerings based on student input, ensuring that health-promoting practices evolve with changing preferences and needs. The Food Research & Action Center (FRAC) emphasizes the essential role of school meals in student health and learning. Their brief highlights that school meal programs are instrumental in supporting obesity prevention, overall student health, and academic achievement by improving children's diets and combating hunger. As the literature suggests, schools serve as a critical venue for fostering healthy habits, especially for students who may not have access to balanced meals at home.

In summary, while students generally perceive the availability of healthy food at school as satisfactory, their responses highlight actionable areas for improvement. By increasing variety, ensuring consistency, and improving communication, schools can further strengthen their food environments. This aligns with the view that when healthy choices are accessible, visible, and supported by school culture, they become the norm, ultimately promoting better dietary behavior and well-being among students.

Table 5 presents the students' evaluation of the school food environment across three key dimensions: taste, price, and availability of healthy food options. The overall mean score of $M = 3.74$ ($SD = 0.78$) indicates a generally high level of satisfaction, implying that the school has created a favorable food environment for learners.

The highest rating was observed in the availability of healthy food options ($M = 3.80$, $SD = 0.82$), reflecting that students recognize and value the presence of nutritious choices in the school canteen. This finding affirms the role of school-based nutrition interventions, as highlighted in the systematic review by Pulz et al. (2022), which confirmed that adolescents are more likely to adopt healthy dietary behaviors when schools actively provide accessible and health-promoting food environments.

Taste followed closely with a mean score of $M = 3.76$ ($SD = 0.85$), denoting that students find the meals generally palatable. Taste is a significant dimension of food choice, and when nutritious meals are prepared in ways that appeal to students, consumption of healthy food increases. Hoelscher et al. (2022) further emphasized that

sensory appeal remains a primary driver of students' willingness to eat school meals and that taste-enhanced healthy offerings lead to better dietary outcomes in school settings.

Meanwhile, the price dimension, although still rated high ($M = 3.66$, $SD = 0.82$), received the lowest mean score among the three. This result implies that while most students find the food reasonably priced, some may still encounter affordability concerns. Ensuring that healthy options remain economically accessible is crucial in sustaining equitable participation in school meal programs, particularly in diverse socioeconomic contexts.

In a nutshell, the findings indicate that students generally perceive the school food environment as supportive of their dietary needs, with notable strengths in nutrition and taste. However, attention to pricing strategies could further improve student access and satisfaction.

Research Question 3: To what extent do senior high students utilize social media in their dietary selection?

Table 6 presents data on the extent of senior high school students' utilization of social media in their dietary selection. The overall mean score of 3.71 ($SD = 0.67$), interpreted as *High*, indicates that social media is highly utilized in their food-related decisions. A majority of the participants (61.65%) reported either *High* or *Very High* levels of engagement with food content on social media platforms, while only a small percentage (5.51%) reported *Low* or *Very Low* usage.

The participants showed a high agreement with statements such as frequently encountering food-related content ($M = 3.97$), spending a significant amount of time on social media daily ($M = 4.02$), and having tried food products or recipes because they were trending ($M = 3.79$). These figures indicate that students are not just passive viewers but are also influenced by what they see online.

Several content-specific indicators further support this finding. High mean scores were recorded for the influence of food pictures ($M = 3.92$), reviews or comments from others ($M = 3.92$), discounts or promotions ($M = 3.96$), and nutritional information ($M = 3.80$). These results indicate that students' decisions are shaped not only by the platforms themselves but also by the social and promotional content embedded within them. This affirms the findings of Hebestreit et al. (2022), who concluded that high exposure to food-related content on social media is associated with increased susceptibility to unhealthy eating patterns, particularly due to the frequent promotion of energy-dense and nutrient-poor foods.

Despite the presence of some positive food content, such as healthy recipes or informative nutrition posts, the unregulated nature of social media also allows for the proliferation of misleading or promotional messages that may not support balanced eating. Zeng et al. (2025) explain that social media algorithms, like those on *TikTok* and *Instagram*, often show users more of the same content they interact with. This can trap

adolescents in a cycle of repeated exposure to certain food trends, leading to diet choices based on popularity rather than nutrition.

These findings highlight the critical need for schools and public health advocates to engage with social media platforms in promoting healthier eating habits. Digital media literacy programs, when integrated into health education, can empower students to critically assess online content, recognize advertising strategies, and make informed dietary decisions. Moreover, public health campaigns that leverage the same platforms used by adolescents can deliver positive nutritional messages in engaging and relatable formats.

In conclusion, the data affirm that social media shapes the dietary choices of senior high school students. As such, its effect must be acknowledged and strategically used to support healthier behaviors through targeted digital interventions and media literacy education.

Research Question 4: What is the participant's level of assessment on their dietary practices?

Table 7 presents the data on the senior high school students' assessment on the dietary practices. The table indicates that senior high school students generally practice healthy eating behaviors, as reflected in the overall mean score of 3.71 ($SD = 0.80$), interpreted as *High*. This denotes that, on average, students frequently engage in favorable dietary practices.

Notably, 19.80% of students rated their dietary habits as *Very High*, while 39.60% assessed them as *High*, comprising a significant 59.40% majority who perceive themselves as consistently maintaining good eating behaviors. Meanwhile, 36.09% rated their practices as *Moderate*, and only a small portion, 4.51%, reported *Low* or *Very Low* levels, indicating that unhealthy habits are limited to a minor segment of the population.

These findings reflect a relatively encouraging dietary pattern among adolescents. Many students reported regular consumption of water, fruits, vegetables, and protein-rich foods, as well as a preference for home-cooked meals over fast food. For example, the indicator "*I prefer home-cooked meals over fast food*" received a high mean of 3.93, and "*I eat protein-rich foods such as fish, eggs, poultry, or beans daily*" had a mean of 3.96. These results align with the observations of Angeles-Agdeppa et al. (2022), who found that Filipino adolescents tend to benefit from traditional household food practices and school meal availability, which support balanced nutrition even when formal nutrition knowledge may be limited.

Despite these strengths, the data also reveal key areas for improvement. The lowest-rated items include "*I eat three balanced meals a day*" ($M = 3.47$) and "*I consume breakfast regularly*" ($M = 3.46$), both at the upper end of the *Moderate* range. This implies that while students generally eat healthily, meal timing and consistency, especially in the morning, remain a challenge. As Liu et al. (2020) have shown, irregular meal patterns, particularly skipping breakfast, are common among adolescents and are linked to poorer

nutritional outcomes, lower academic performance, and increased risk of obesity. These findings suggest that targeted interventions promoting consistent eating routines, such as school breakfast initiatives or time-management strategies, could further improve student well-being.

Another key insight lies in the students' strong intention to maintain or improve their diet. The item "I am willing to improve my eating habits for better health" received a high mean of 4.08, and "I feel that my diet directly affects my energy and performance in school" rated 3.90. These results indicate that students not only practice good habits but also recognize the value of nutrition in their daily functioning. As UNICEF (2023) emphasizes, adolescents are more likely to adopt and sustain healthy eating behaviors when they are both aware of their impact and supported by an enabling environment at school and at home.

In summary, the overall high mean score and the significant 59.40% of students rating their practices as *High* to *Very High* illustrate a solid foundation for healthy eating among senior high school students. However, attention should be given to promoting regular meal patterns and addressing barriers to consistent dietary routines. These findings highlight the importance of reinforcing what students are already doing well while guiding them toward greater dietary consistency and nutritional awareness.

Research Question 5: Do the levels of senior high students' nutrition knowledge, their utilization of social media in food selection, and the school food environment significantly influence their dietary practices?

Ho₁: The level of senior high students' nutrition knowledge does not significantly influence their dietary practices.

Ho₂: The students' utilization of social media in food selection does not significantly influence their dietary practices.

Ho₃: The school food environment does not significantly influence their dietary practices.

Table 8 is the regression analysis that illustrates the influence of students' assessment of their nutrition knowledge, utilization of social media in food selection, and the school food environment, specifically in terms of taste, price, and availability of healthy food options, on their dietary practices. The overall model was statistically significant ($F = 56.69$, $p < .001$), with an R^2 of 0.419, indicating that approximately 41.9% of the variability in dietary practices can be explained by the combined set of predictors; hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. The availability of healthy food options showed the strongest influence ($\beta = .268$, $p = .001$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for this variable. This finding indicates that for every unit increase in food healthy options, there is a corresponding increase of .268 in dietary practices, implying that when students perceive nutritious food as accessible within the school setting, they are more likely to adopt healthier eating behaviors. This result echoes the conclusions of Pulz et al. (2022), who emphasized that supportive food environments are positively associated with improved adolescent dietary quality.

Social media utilization also demonstrated a significant effect ($\beta = .259, p < .001$). This means that for every unit increase in social media utilization for their food selection, there is a corresponding .259 increase in their dietary practices. Students who actively engage with food-related content on digital platforms were more likely to report health-conscious eating patterns. This finding supports Zeng et al. (2025), who highlighted how exposure to food content on social media shapes adolescents' dietary habits by reinforcing particular behaviors through repeated messaging.

Price emerged as another significant predictor ($\beta = .201, p = .011$), indicating that for every unit increase of price, there is a corresponding increase of .201 in their dietary practices, implying that affordability plays a vital role in food selection among students. When food is perceived as reasonably priced, students are more inclined to consume it regularly. Turner et al. (2023) noted that affordability is a key enabler in promoting healthy food choices, especially in settings with limited financial resources. In this case, the null hypothesis can be rejected.

On the other hand, the variables of taste ($\beta = .039, p = .619$) and nutrition knowledge ($\beta = .057, p = .141$) did not significantly influence dietary practices, and therefore the null hypotheses for these were not rejected. While taste is generally a strong motivator in food selection, its lack of significance in this context might be due to limited food variety and choice in the school setting. The study tested the null hypotheses that nutrition knowledge and taste, as a component of the school food environment, do not significantly influence the dietary practices of senior high school students.

The null hypothesis for nutrition knowledge stated that there is no significant relationship between students' nutrition knowledge and their dietary practices. Based on the multiple linear regression analysis, this hypothesis was not rejected as the p-value for nutrition knowledge was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Despite the low levels of nutrition knowledge identified among respondents, this factor did not show a statistically significant predictive relationship with their reported dietary behaviors. This result supports previous findings that, although nutrition knowledge is important, it does not directly translate into behavior change (Spronk et al., 2014). Various factors—such as lack of motivation, socio-environmental pressures, and limited access to healthy food—can mediate or weaken the link between what adolescents know and how they behave.

Similarly, the null hypothesis for taste posited that taste does not significantly influence students' dietary practices. This hypothesis was also not rejected. While students rated taste highly in their assessment of the school food environment, this variable did not show a statistically significant influence on dietary practices in the regression model. This may be attributed to the idea that while taste enhances food preference, it is not necessarily the deciding factor in food choices among adolescents. Factors like price, availability, and social influence often play more prominent roles in real-life decision-making (Mikkelsen et al., 2020). In the context of this study, it appears that students may appreciate tasty food but still be more influenced by practical constraints such as affordability and peer-driven media exposure when deciding what to eat.

These findings are consistent with Social Cognitive Theory and the Ecological Model of Health Behavior, which emphasize the interplay of personal, environmental, and social influences on health behavior. Both taste and knowledge are important but may be insufficient on their own to drive significant behavioral outcomes without support from external and environmental reinforcements. As for nutrition knowledge, the findings align with Angeles-Agdeppa et al. (2022), who found that adolescent dietary behaviors are often shaped more by social and environmental cues than by cognitive knowledge alone.

While the model explains a substantial portion of the variance in dietary practices, a remaining 58.1% remains unaccounted for, pointing to other potential factors not included in this study. These may include household food security, parental dietary patterns, peer influence, emotional and psychological conditions, and cultural or religious food norms. For instance, Pearson et al. (2019) reported that family eating practices and parental modeling are strong determinants of children's eating behavior. Similarly, Lally et al. (2011) and Michels et al. (2012) showed that peer norms and stress-induced eating significantly impact adolescents' food choices. Cultural context also matters, as outlined by Kittler et al. (2017), who noted that cultural and religious traditions shape acceptable dietary practices.

These results offer three key insights. First, environmental support, particularly the availability and affordability of nutritious food, is a more reliable driver of adolescent dietary behavior than internal preferences like taste or knowledge. Second, social media is a significant behavioral cue, providing both information and influence in adolescents' food choices. Third, even in the absence of strong nutrition literacy, adolescents can still demonstrate good dietary habits when their environment enables healthy decision-making.

In summary, the analysis leads to the rejection of the null hypotheses for the availability of healthy food options, social media utilization, and food pricing, confirming their significant influence on dietary practices.

The null hypotheses for taste and nutrition knowledge were not rejected due to their non-significant influence. These findings suggest that strategies aimed at improving adolescent nutrition should go beyond individual knowledge and preferences by focusing on improving access to healthy food and leveraging the influence of digital and environmental factors. By addressing these external elements, interventions can more effectively support healthy dietary behaviors among students.

Conclusions

The results of this study reveal that while senior high school students generally engage in healthy dietary behaviors, these practices are more strongly influenced by external and environmental factors—specifically the affordability and availability of nutritious food and the impact of social media—rather than their internal knowledge about nutrition, which was found to be low. This suggests that practical and accessible enablers in the environment play a more pivotal role in shaping food choices among adolescents

than cognitive understanding alone. The significance of social media as a dietary influence affirms its potential as both a risk and a tool—it can either expose students to misleading dietary trends or promote healthier food behaviors depending on the content they consume. This highlights the need for digital media literacy programs that empower students to critically evaluate online nutrition content and resist harmful food messaging.

Similarly, the school food environment was found to be a crucial determinant of dietary behavior, particularly in the availability of healthy food options. When nutritious foods are accessible, affordable, and appealing, students are more likely to incorporate them into their daily routines. These results align with Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and McLeroy's Ecological Model, both of which emphasize the importance of environmental support systems and social modeling in behavior change.

Importantly, the study also underscores a missed opportunity in current nutrition education programs. Although students are willing to adopt healthy eating habits and recognize the importance of nutrition for their well-being, their limited knowledge suggests that existing interventions are insufficient. A stronger emphasis on school-based nutrition education—integrated into various subjects, reinforced through experiential learning, and aligned with digital engagement—could help bridge this gap. Moreover, fostering partnerships among educators, nutritionists, policy-makers, and media platforms could amplify the reach and impact of nutrition advocacy among adolescents.

In conclusion, to effectively support and sustain healthy dietary practices among senior high school students, interventions must extend beyond knowledge dissemination. They should instead prioritize building supportive food environments, leveraging social media as a positive influence, and integrating nutrition literacy in ways that are engaging, practical, and relevant to students' lived experiences. Such a multifaceted approach is essential not only to improve individual health outcomes but also to contribute meaningfully to broader public health goals, including those under Sustainable Development Goal 2: Zero Hunger.

Recommendations

In light of the conclusions, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

1. For School Administrators, that they

1.1 Integrate comprehensive nutrition education into the senior high school curriculum to improve students' understanding of balanced diets, reading food labels, and critical evaluation of online food information.

1.2 Enhance the school food environment by:

- Increasing the variety and presentation of healthy options.
- Offering affordable pricing for healthier meals.
- Incorporating feedback mechanisms from students for continuous improvement of cafeteria services.

2. For Teachers and Dietetics Instructors

2.1 Utilize social media platforms to disseminate accurate nutrition information through student-friendly formats such as short videos, infographics, and challenges.

- 2.2 Encourage critical media literacy by teaching students how to evaluate food advertisements and health claims online.
3. For Nutritionist-Dietitians
 - 3.1 Collaborate with schools in designing school-wide wellness programs, workshops, and interactive nutrition campaigns.
 - 3.2 Monitor students' progress and provide individual or group counseling to address specific dietary issues.
4. For Future Researchers
 - 4.1 Conduct similar studies in public schools and across different regions to assess variations in food environments and cultural influences.
 - 4.2 Investigate the content quality of food-related social media posts and their direct psychological effects on students' eating patterns.
 - 4.3 Explore the impact of nutrition interventions via social media to evaluate its effectiveness in improving adolescents' dietary behavior.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was conducted following the ethical principles outlined in the Belmont Report (1978), as cited by Amdur and Bankert (2021). These principles—respect for persons, beneficence, and justice—were central to ensuring ethical standards throughout the research process.

Respect for persons involved, safeguarding the autonomy of participants by securing their voluntary and informed consent. Participants were provided with a clear explanation of the study's objectives, data collection procedures, expected duration of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. During the orientation, participants were informed of their role, the instruments to be used, and any foreseeable risks or advantages involved.

Beneficence emphasized minimizing risks and maximizing potential benefits. The researcher adopted appropriate measures to reduce any physical, psychological, or social risks to participants. The potential benefits of the study were carefully weighed against these risks to ensure participant well-being remained a priority throughout the research.

Justice ensured fair selection and equal treatment of participants. The sampling process avoided any form of discrimination or exploitation, ensuring that all participants had an equal opportunity to contribute to the study and benefit from its outcomes. The researcher also maintained strict confidentiality and data protection measures. Participants' identities were anonymized by coding the responses, and no names or personal identifiers were used in data processing or reporting. Privacy was respected at every stage, and all information collected was securely stored and used solely for academic purposes, following ethical research standards.

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